

Assessing Physical Fitness Differences between High School and Dakhil Madrasah Boys in Bangladesh*Shaybal Chanda¹ & Md.Sardar Ashikur Rahman²*

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Abstract

Background: Physical fitness is essential for adolescents as it promotes overall health, prevents chronic diseases, and improves mental and cognitive well-being. Aim: To compare the physical fitness and motor performance of boys from High Schools and Madrasahs in Rangpur District of Bangladesh. **Methods:** 400 physically fit boys aged 14–16 from 10 high schools and 10 madrasahs were randomly selected. Using the JCR fitness test, measurements of age, weight, height, and BMI were taken. Vertical jump was recorded as the best of three attempts, chin-ups counted in one trial, and shuttle run time measured over a 100-meter course between two 10-meter markers. **Statistics:** Data were analyzed using the Mann-Whitney U test due to non-normal distribution, with a power of 0.89 and a medium effect size. **Results:** High School students had a higher mean vertical jump (42.62 cm) and faster shuttle run time (26.96 milliseconds), while Madrasah students showed higher mean chin-ups (8.22) and overall JCR fitness scores (232.69). Significant differences were found in vertical jump ($U = 17587.00$, $p = .037$), favoring High School students, and in overall JCR score ($U = 17461.00$, $p = .028$), favoring Madrasah students. No significant differences were observed in height, weight, BMI, chin-ups, or shuttle run time despite differences in mean values. **Conclusion:** The study shows Madrasah boys performed better overall in fitness, High School boys excelled in leg power (vertical jump), and both groups had similar chin-up and shuttle run results.

Key words: Adolescent fitness, JCR Fitness Test, Vertical Jump, Chin-up, Shuttle Run, Motor Fitness.

Background

Physical fitness is a vital component of adolescent health and development, encompassing the ability to perform daily life activities with vigor and resilience, while minimizing fatigue and injury risk (Neumann et al., 2022; Ortega et al., 2008). It has a crucial role in preventing chronic diseases such as cardiovascular disorders, diabetes, and certain cancers, while also strengthening the immune system and supporting healthy aging (Bushman, 2020; Forte et al., 2022; O et al., 2019). Additionally, it enhances mental well-being, boosts cognitive function, and contributes to better academic and work performance (Kwak et al., 2009; Mandolesi et al., 2018; Pronk et al., 2004). The American College of Sports Medicine highlights five key components of physical fitness: cardiorespiratory endurance, muscular strength, muscular endurance, flexibility, and body composition, each integral to overall health and functionality (Medicine, 2013). On the other hand, in the field of sports training, fundamental components of physical fitness include strength, endurance, speed, flexibility, and coordination, which play a pivotal role in physical performance and skillful movement (Fischetti & Greco, 2017; Nazymok et al., 2024).

In Bangladesh, secondary education is provided through three parallel streams: general high schools, vocational schools, and Dakhil Madrasahs. These offer education mainly from 6th to 10th grade, with Dakhil formally recognized as equivalent to high school (Chowdhury & Sarkar, 2018). According to the Bangladesh Ministry of Education (2023), in 2023, a total of 2,041,450 students appeared in the SSC and equivalent examinations across Bangladesh, including candidates from 9

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General Education Boards, the Madrasah Education Board, and the Technical Education Board. Among them, 1,009,803 were male and 1,031,647 were female, with pass rates of 78.87% and 81.88% respectively. From the 9 General Education Boards, 1,633,919 students took part, including 776,519 males (79.34% pass rate) and 857,400 females (82.39%). In the Dakhil examination under the Madrasah Education Board, 285,087 students appeared - 139,655 males (72.29%) and 145,432 females (77.02%). From the Technical Education Board (SSC Vocational and Dakhil Vocational), 122,444 students participated, comprising 93,629 males with a pass rate of 84.78% and 28,815 females with a pass rate of 91.44%. This reveals that among all male students who appeared in the SSC and equivalent examinations in 2023, **76.89% were from the General Education Boards, 13.83% from the Madrasah Education Board, and 9.28% from the Technical Education Board.** (SSC Result 2023, 2023). Notably, the SSC (Secondary School Certificate) examination, also known as the 10th Standard in countries like Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan, is roughly equivalent to the Cambridge O-Level (Ordinary Level) qualification is part of the **British (UK) education system**. The government has made it mandatory to recruit physical education teachers in all general schools, vocational schools, and Madrasahs, ensuring equal access to structured physical education for all students. Additionally, students from Madrasahs, technical schools, and schools have equal opportunities to participate in inter-institutional sports competitions organized at various levels by the Bangladesh National School, Madrasa, and Technical Education Sports Association (Shefali, 2021; Sun, 2022).

Physical fitness in adolescence affects not only health but also thinking skills, school performance, and social development (Ahmed, 2013; Haverkamp et al., 2021). Research shows that active teens do better in school, have better memory and focus, and are more confident socially than less active teens (Donnelly et al., 2016). Conversely, poor physical fitness is linked with increased risks of depression, anxiety, and chronic health conditions (Sawchuk & Olatunji, 2011).

Despite equal provisions like government-funded physical education teachers and joint sports competitions, it remains uncertain whether students from schools and Madrasahs achieve similar levels of physical fitness. Although both offer similar physical education programs, Madrasahs focus more on religious studies while schools follow a more balanced curriculum, suggesting that equal resources may not guarantee the same fitness outcomes. Physical exercise is crucial for children's holistic development and the nation's future, as even a portion of children develop poorly, it can harm their growth and weaken the country's progress. Given the government's efforts to provide Madrasah students with resources and opportunities comparable to general school students, this study aims to investigate whether these efforts result in equitable physical fitness outcomes. **The primary research question guiding this investigation is: What are the differences in physical fitness levels between high school and Dakhil Madrasah boys in Bangladesh?** The objective is to assess and compare the physical fitness levels of high school and Dakhil Madrasah boys in Bangladesh, identifying any disparities that may exist despite similar opportunities.

Materials and Methods

Participants

A total of 400 boys from the 9th and 10th standards were selected as subjects for the present study, with 200 students from 10 high schools and 200 from 10 madrasahs in the Rangpur District of Bangladesh. The selected institutions were located in urban, suburban, and rural areas of the district. The age of the participants ranged from 14 to 16 years. The average height of male High School students was 164.27 cm (± 6.27 cm), while male Madrasah students had a slightly lower mean height of 163.87 cm with greater variability (± 8.61 cm). In terms of weight, male High School students averaged 52.40 kg (± 8.76 kg), and male Madrasah students averaged 51.71 kg but with a wider spread (± 12.62 kg). For BMI, male High School students had a mean of 19.39 (± 2.84), whereas male Madrasah students had a slightly higher average BMI of 20.14, accompanied by much larger variability (± 11.32).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Before data collection, permission was obtained from the respective institutional authorities. Participation was voluntary, and interested students were considered. Using stratified random sampling, 20 male students were selected from each institution, including 10 from the 9th standard and 10 from the 10th standard. Only students who were physically fit and free from any illness or injury at the time of data collection were included. All participants signed an informed consent form and were allowed to withdraw from the study at any time without obligation.

Study Design

The physical fitness parameters assessed in this study encompassed age, body weight, body height, Body Mass Index (BMI), vertical jump height, chin-up repetitions, and shuttle run duration. These variables were evaluated using the JCR fitness test protocol developed by Phillips (1947). This test holds Reliability of .91-.97 and Validity of .81. Vertical jump height was measured to the nearest centimeter, while chin-ups were recorded as the total number of correctly performed repetitions. Shuttle run time was precisely timed to the nearest hundredth of a second. BMI was calculated following the World Health Organization's (WHO) standard formula, which divides weight in kilograms by the square of height in meters. To facilitate data collection, the study employed various equipment, including a digital weighing machine, height scale, measuring tape, chalk, chin-up/pull-up bar, stopwatch, and a wooden block.

Test Protocol

Data were collected by administering the JCR fitness test. First, the subjects were briefed on the test procedures. Then, using a weighing machine and height scale, each participant was called individually to record their age, weight, and height. Following this, measurements for vertical jump (in centimeters), chin-up repetitions, and shuttle run time (in seconds) were collected according to the standardized JCR fitness test protocols.

JCR Fitness Test Protocol

Before the official test began, all participants were given a clear demonstration of each test component to ensure proper understanding. Additionally, a short, low-intensity practice session was offered. Those who were interested were allowed to practice voluntarily before performing the actual test.

1. **Vertical Jump:** Each participant applied lime powder to the fingertips to clearly mark the highest point they could reach. Standing beside a marked wall, they were instructed to jump as high as possible and touch the wall with their powdered fingertips.
2. **Chin-up:** Participants gripped the chin-up bar with an overhand grip, palms facing outward, and were instructed to pull their body upward until their chin cleared the bar, then lower themselves fully before the next repetition.
3. **Shuttle Run:** Participants started at the line between two markers placed 10 meters apart. At the signal, they ran back and forth between the markers 10 times in one trial, covering a total distance of 100 meters as quickly as possible. The time taken to complete the shuttle run was recorded using a stopwatch, measured to the nearest hundredth of a second.

Data Collection Procedure

For each test item under the JCR Fitness Test, data were collected using standardized procedures to ensure accuracy and reliability.

1. **Vertical Jump:** Each participant performed three trials of the vertical jump. The best jump height among the three was recorded and measured to the nearest centimeter.
2. **Chin-up:** Participants were given a single trial to perform as many correct chin-ups as possible. Only properly executed repetitions, where the chin clearly passed above the bar and full extension was achieved during descent, were counted.

- Shuttle Run:** Each participant completed one trial of the shuttle run, which involved running back and forth between two markers placed 10 meters apart, completing 10 lengths (a total of 100 meters). The time taken to complete the trial was recorded in milliseconds using a digital stopwatch.
- JCR Test Score:** The JCR fitness test score was calculated by first converting the shuttle run time into a Normalized Relative Score, which was then combined with the scores from the vertical jump and chin-up tests.

Statistical Analysis

The raw data were analyzed using standard statistical techniques. Measures of central tendency and dispersion were calculated using the mean and standard deviation, respectively. Before selecting the appropriate statistical tests, tests for normality and homogeneity were conducted. The results indicated that the data did not follow a normal distribution, and homogeneity of variance was not met. As a result, nonparametric statistical methods were applied. Specifically, the Mann-Whitney U test with significance of $\alpha=.05$ was used to assess group differences due to its suitability for non-normally distributed data. With the sample size of 200 in each group, the power of the test ($1 - \beta$) was calculated as 0.89, corresponding to a medium effect size (Cohen’s d) of 0.5.

Results

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Vertical Jump, Chin-up, Shuttle Run, and JCR Test Score

		Descriptive	
Vertical Jump (centimeters)	High School	Mean	42.62
		SD	±6.53
	Madrasah	Mean	41.54
		SD	±12.65
Chin-up (number)	High School	Mean	7.33
		SD	±3.75
	Madrasah	Mean	8.22
		SD	±12.40
Shuttle Run (milliseconds)	High School	Mean	26.96
		SD	±2.12
	Madrasah	Mean	27.54
		SD	±10.63
JCR Fitness Test (score)	High School	Mean	228.42
		SD	±13.04
	Madrasah	Mean	232.69
		SD	±101.60

The descriptive statistics indicate that High School students demonstrated a slightly higher mean vertical jump performance (42.62 cm, SD = ±6.53) compared to Madrasah students (41.54 cm, SD = ±12.65). Conversely, Madrasah students achieved a higher mean in chin-up performance (8.22 repetitions, SD = ±12.40) than their High School counterparts (7.33 repetitions, SD = ±3.75). In the shuttle run, High School students performed better, with a lower mean time (26.96 milliseconds, SD = ±2.12) than Madrasah students (27.54 milliseconds, SD = ±10.63), reflecting greater agility. Finally, the mean JCR fitness test score was slightly higher among Madrasah students (232.69, SD = ±101.60) than High School students (228.42, SD = ±13.04). Notably, the standard deviations for all variables were substantially higher among Madrasah students, indicating greater variability and inconsistency in performance within that group.

Table 2. Mann-Whitney U Test between High School and Madrasah Boys

	Test Statistics ^a						
	Height	Weight	BMI	Vertical Jump	Chin Up	Shuttle Run	JCR Test Score
Mann-Whitney U Test	19937.00	18324.50	19933.50	17587.00	19778.00	18471.50	17461.00
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.956	.147	.954	.037	.847	.186	.028

a. Grouping Variable: Institution Type: High School VS Madrasah

The Mann-Whitney U test was applied to compare physical and fitness characteristics between High School and Madrasah boys. Although descriptive statistics consistently showed that High School boys had superior mean values across all variables - including height, weight, BMI, vertical jump, chin-up, shuttle run, and the overall JCR test score - statistically significant differences were found only in vertical jump ($U = 17587.00$, $p = .037$) and JCR test score ($U = 17461.00$, $p = .028$). No significant differences were observed in height, weight, BMI, chin-up, or shuttle run performances, despite the higher average scores of High School boys. These results indicate that while High School boys generally performed better, the differences were statistically meaningful only in explosive leg power and overall motor fitness.

Discussion

This study is important because it provides valuable insights into the physical fitness differences between student groups, helping educators and coaches develop more effective, tailored training programs to enhance youth fitness and athletic performance. Study discovers that High School boys performed significantly better in vertical jump, while Madrasah boys had a significantly higher overall JCR fitness score; Madrasah boys also had a higher average chin-up count, whereas High School boys had higher average values in height, weight, BMI, and shuttle run, but these differences were not statistically significant. Bangladesh National School, Madrasa, and Technical Education Sports Association organize winter and summer sports competitions, giving equal opportunities to all three categories of educational institutions – general schools, vocational schools, and Madrasahs (Shefali, 2021; Sun, 2022). Participation and success of vocational schools are not worth mentioning, where as both schools and madrasahs participate actively in competitions; however, success for madrasahs remains relatively scarce (Hossain, 2018; Musharraf, 2016). In Bangladesh, the sports and physical exercise teaching contact time between physical education teachers and students in schools and madrasahs is not at a satisfactory level, almost the same (Shahjalal et al., 2024). Probably, school boys get more facilities for physical activity and sports than the madrasah boys, despite equal support given from the government; therefore, school boys are better in most variables. It would not be possible to earn expected prosperity, poorly developing **13.83% of boys in a nation from Madrasahs (SSC Result 2023, 2023)**. The government should implement appropriate policies and measures to ensure that all young boys receive equal opportunities to maintain their health, fostering a fit and healthy nation. This will help reduce national healthcare costs, improve quality of life, and enable them to reach their full potential in adulthood to serve the country effectively.

Conclusion

Evidence from the study points to Madrasah boys performing better overall in general fitness as measured by the JCR test, while High School boys were stronger in vertical jump, which measures leg power. In chin-ups and shuttle run tests, both groups showed similar performance. This means each group has different strengths in physical fitness. Educational institutions should implement targeted fitness programs that address specific strengths and weaknesses of students to improve overall physical health and performance.

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